

The Influence of Solvent Composition on the Rate of Dipole-Dipole and Ion-Dipole Reactions

Kamala K. Satpathy and P. L. Nayak

The effect of solvent composition on the rates of some dipole-dipole and ion-dipole reactions has been studied in various pure and mixed solvents like methanol-water, dioxan-water and acetone-water mixtures. There is no simple correlation of the rate constant with the dielectric constant but the rate is related to Grunwald-Winstein 'Y' factor. The parameters of the transition state theory were found to be linearly related to 'Y' values of the solvent composition and the results have been interpreted in the light of Winstein-Fainberg treatment. The decrease in rate constant with increase in polarity of the solvent in case of ion-dipole reaction has been explained in terms of Hughes-Ingold theory.

The influence of solvent composition on the rate of bimolecular nucleophilic substitution reactions has been recently reviewed by Parker¹. We have reported the effect of solvent composition on the rate of some dipole-dipole and ion-dipole reactions.

For the bimolecular reaction, $A + B \rightarrow M^\ddagger \rightarrow$ products, the equation for the specific rate constant may be written²

$$\ln k' = \ln \left(x \frac{kT}{h} K_0^\ddagger \right) - \frac{1}{kT} \left(\frac{D-1}{2D+1} \right) \left[\frac{\mu_A^2}{\alpha_A^3} + \frac{\mu_B^2}{\alpha_B^3} - \frac{\mu_{M^\ddagger}^2}{\alpha_{M^\ddagger}^3} \right] + \frac{\phi_A + \phi_B - \phi_{M^\ddagger}}{kT} \quad (1)$$

Provided the nonelectrostatic terms are negligibly small, a plot of $\ln k$ v.s. $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ should give a straight line. The plots of $\log k$ vs. $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ for the reaction between 2,4-dinitro chlorobenzene with benzylamine for different binary solvent mixtures were continuous curves, indicating that dielectric constant is not an adequate measure of the solvent's role on this reaction. This type of behaviour has also been noted by Lockhart³ for the substitution reaction of 1-chloro 2,4-dinitro benzene and *p*-toluidine in dioxan water mixtures.

The various properties which contribute to the ability of a solvent to solvate ions can be measured by the quantity 'Y' termed the "ionising power"⁴ of the solvent, which is a function of solvent solute interaction defined by the equation

$$\log k = \log k_0 + mY.$$

1. A. J. Parker, *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **69**, 1.
2. A. S. Amis, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic Press, New York, N.Y., 1966.
3. J. C. Lockhart, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1980.
4. S. Winstein and A. H. Fainberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 5937.

Straight line plots of $\log k$ vs. 'Y' for acetone-water, methanol-water and dioxan-water were obtained. An extrapolation of the line to the value for pure dioxan yields a 'Y' value of (-5.32). This value is the same as calculated by Lockhart³. Nucleophilic aromatic substitution may thus provide another measure of solvating power in non-hydroxytic media analogous to Kosower's Z values. Recently the Z values of Kosower⁵ based on charge transfer spectra of pyridinium iodides are being used for measure of solvent polarity. The $\log k$ values for methanol-water, acetone-water and dioxan-water were also plotted against the Kosower's Z values. Excellent plots were obtained in each case which justifies the importance of Z values as the measure of solvent polarity over dielectric constant. The same conclusion has also been drawn by Martin and co-workers⁶ for the radical decomposition of *t*-butyl-*o*-phenyl thioperbenzoate.

The relationship between the thermodynamic quantities of activation and the 'Y' values for the binary solvent mixtures has been discussed theoretically by Fainberg and Winstein⁴. In the present study the relationship was tested by plotting the values of ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger vs. Y values for different solvent compositions and linear plots were obtained in each case.

Linear plots were also obtained between ΔH^\ddagger vs. ΔS^\ddagger for the solvent composition methanol-water, acetone-water and dioxan-water mixtures indicating that they change in the same direction with the change in polarity of the solvent⁷.

The SN_2 reaction between phenacyl bromide and sodium benzoate has been studied in acetone-water mixtures. The results have been recorded in Table IV. The rate constant decreases with increasing ionising power of the solvent. This retardation of rate with increasing ionising power of the solvent can be neatly explained according to Hughes-Ingold theory⁸, because in the more polar solvent, differences in the solvation of reactants and transition state would be enhanced, increasing the activation energy and hence reducing the rate of reaction. The same argument has also been advanced by Glover⁹ in the reaction of barbiturate ion with β -nitro styrene.

EXPERIMENTAL

The solvents used were of 'Analar' quality. Triple distilled water was used for dilution of solvents.

2,4-dinitro chlorobenzene was crystallised several times from petroleum ether before use. Phenacyl bromide was prepared and purified by the method of Rout and co-workers¹⁰. Benzylamine was twice vacuum distilled before use. Sodium benzoate was prepared by the usual procedure.

- 5a. E. M. Kosower, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **80**, 3253, 3261.
- b. E. M. Kosower, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3147.
6. D. L. Tulben, W. G. Bentraude and J. C. Martin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1938.
7. J. E. Leffler, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, **20**, 1202.
- 8a. C. K. Ingold, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, N.Y., 1953.
- b. E. D. Hughes and C. K. Ingold, *Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1942, **27**, 665.
9. M. J. Kamlet and D. J. Glover, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4556.
10. R. K. Mohanty, G. B. Behera and M. K. Rout, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 259.

TABLE I

Effect of solvent in the SN_2 reaction of 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene with benzylamine in acetone-water mixture

Values of $k \times 10^4$ in lit. mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹

[Benzylamine] = 0.08(M), [2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene] = 0.04(M)

% Acetone V/V	$k \times 10^4$ in lit. mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹				E K.cal/ mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger_{35}$ Cals/ degree/ mole	ΔH^\ddagger_{35} K.cal/ mole
	25°	30°	35°	40°			
100	—	7.24	13.81	16.70	15.60	23.50	15.00
90	—	10.89	17.91	26.32	16.10	20.60	15.50
80	—	12.25	19.20	28.86	17.50	16.70	16.90
70	9.21	14.90	25.61	—	19.30	10.70	18.72
60	—	17.05	28.51	47.90	20.30	5.10	19.60
50	—	18.42	30.70	53.74	20.70	4.40	20.10

TABLE II

Effect of solvent on SN_2 reaction between, 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene with benzylamine in methanol-water mixture

[Benzylamine] = 0.08(M), [2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene] = 0.04(M)

% Methanol V/V	$k \times 10^4$ in lit. mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹					E K.cal/ mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ Cals/ degree/ mole	ΔH^\ddagger_{35} K.cals/ mole
	25°	27°	30°	35°	40°			
100	—	—	9.60	13.40	21.40	16.10	21.50	15.50
90	—	5.80	—	12.28	19.20	17.50	17.20	16.90
85	—	—	7.60	12.06	18.30	17.90	15.70	17.30
80	4.80	—	7.34	11.51	17.00	18.20	15.00	17.50
75	4.60	—	7.25	10.90	16.90	18.40	14.40	17.80
70	4.19	—	6.72	10.36	16.63	18.90	12.90	18.20

TABLE III

Specific reaction rate and activation parameters for the SN_2 reaction of 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene with benzylamine in dioxan-water mixture

[Benzylamine] = 0.08(M), [2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene] = 0.04(M)

% Dioxan V/V	Values of $k \times 10^4$ in lit.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹			E K.cal/ mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger_{35}$ Cals./ deg.	ΔH^\ddagger K.cal/ mole
	30°	35°	40°			
50	23.03	36.80	61.40	18.40	11.90	17.80
60	18.99	35.70	55.20	19.20	9.60	18.60
70	15.35	27.63	45.06	20.90	5.60	20.30
80	6.14	11.33	16.88	22.00	3.70	21.40

TABLE IV

Values of specific reaction rate and activation parameters for the SN_2 reaction of phenacyl bromide with sodium benzoate in acetone-water mixture

[Sodium benzoate] = 0.04(M), [[Phenacyl bromide] = 0.08(M)

% Acetone V/V	Values of $k \times 10^3$ in lit.mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹					E K.cals/ mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ Cals/ deg/mole	ΔH^\ddagger K.cals/ mole
	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°			
90	3.83	5.91	7.66	—	—	12.40	29.70	11.80
85	2.79	4.38	6.85	—	—	16.10	18.00	15.50
80	1.47	2.56	3.84	—	—	18.40	12.30	17.80
70	—	1.148	1.92	3.23	5.12	20.30	7.00	19.60
60	—	1.047	1.86	2.75	—	22.10	1.20	21.50

Kinetic measurement : 50 ml. of a solution of 0.04(M) 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene and 0.08(M) with respect to benzylamine were thermostated in required temperatures. Aliquots were withdrawn at intervals and the reactions were analysed for chloride by Volhard's method after partition between 15 ml. benzene, 10 ml. water and 5 ml. of silver nitrate solution. The aqueous layer together with 2×10 ml. washings were titrated with ammonium thiocyanate solution.

After about 70% of reaction, N-(2,4-dinitro phenyl) benzylamine began to separate from the reaction mixture. Such crystallisation was without effect on the rate of reaction, as judged from the linearity of the plots of $\log(a-x)/(b-x)$ against time.

Product analysis : A solution containing 0.04(M) 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene and 0.08(M) with respect to benzylamine was prepared. The reaction mixture was set aside for 48 hrs. at the room temperature. The precipitate (yellow needles) was then filtered off, washed with water to remove traces of reaction solution and amine salt product and analysed for N-(2,4-dinitro phenyl) benzylamine, m.p. 112°. (Found : C, 57.05; H, 4.10; N, 15.31; $C_{13}H_{11}O_4N_3$ requires C, 57.14; H, 4.0; N, 15.38).

The authors are grateful to Prof. M. K. Rout for his guidance and authorities of the Sambalpur University for financial assistance.

Department of Chemistry,
G.M. College,
Sambalpur, Orissa.

Received October 21, 1970